
ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades the word “Globalization” has become a common word that is heard in many international conferences and large gatherings. A number of definitions of globalization related to the provision of products or services are given by various people of different sectors. The impact of globalization is also felt on educational industry. The trend of the students and their parents has changed from mere getting a seat for their ward in reputed college to get a seat in a college which gives placement assurance and many more tie ups with foreign universities and dual programme etc. They prefer the college with good academic record and placement record. Education is a complicated system with distinctive properties of objectives, structure, organization, operation modes and operational effectiveness. There has existed a bigger gap between theoretical objectives and implementation practice, which is pushing education further away from the society-desired ideals of equality, democracy and civilization. This paper covered a concept and importance of the education system and the challenges faced by the education sector etc., In a country like India where the students who emerge from colleges are often being accused of not being industry ready and far removed from practicalities, the academic industry must put its best foot forward. Industry academia relationship has over the years involved setting up research labs, sponsoring initiatives, offering projects, mentoring students, instituting scholarships and awards. This is a gateway for aspiring students.

KEYWORDS: Challenges, Achievements and Indian Education System.

INTRODUCTION

Education’s administrative and operational structure reflects a serious imbalance and disorder within and/or among secondary education, vocational training and tertiary education. All of these together are mixed to produce a so-called miscellaneous, confused, un-synchronous, inconsistent, dispersed and unconnected system of components, within which each component unit places more attention to local and insular benefits than to basic and long-term benefits of the whole community. (Recently, in spite of the Government’s call for every sector’s attempts to stop price storm, education sector insists on increasing textbook price huge increase in admission fee academic fee term fee etc. Spending on education has continuously increased while education quality reflects a total opposite. All of these negatives that have been in existence for decades despite specific attempt indicate an “inside-out crisis” of the educational system. Fortunately however, within this dark situation, there is still light (scattered at some level there are successful units), which may ensure a potential of educational development in this country. For the last few years, several positive changes have been witnessed though the “core”, where state of inactivity has long been rooted, has not been touched upon. Accordingly, an impetus for a “look-changing” in education – an urgent demand of the society as a whole – has not yet provoked.

It has to be honestly accepted that the main reason of crisis is the poor management and leadership. Serious mistakes are identified in most aspects of the process, including educational conceptualization, philosophy, system design, management and operation. Subsequently, they produce negative effects on the whole educational system.

In response to higher education and globalization particularly in the developed countries, they have undergone significant change. Increasingly, the needs of the employers in a changing labor market are a key consideration for curriculum development and institutional support. Nowadays graduates in the labor market are expected to be flexible,

to direct and steer their own work as well as that of others, to take responsibility and to mould jobs to make best use of their competencies in the global market economy. Most will need to have transferable skills, the ability to communicate effectively and to master the ever-changing new technologies (Brennan et.al. 2005). Thus globalization of higher education implies the application of market forces towards increased individualization, competition, and a closer link with the world of business, at the heart of this discussion. Cultural differences and intellectual traditions in different countries, however, are not easy to overcome.

The present scenario has forced the educational sector to re- think and re-do the curriculum of the students in such a way that it should be targeted to train the students to face the industrial requirements. The expectation of employer has been shifted from absorbing an intelligent or top ranker to the students with smart work than hard work.

THE TOP CHALLENGES FACED BY THE EDUCATION INDUSTRY ARE:

- Creating learning environments that promote active learning, critical thinking, collaborative learning and knowledge creation.
- Developing 21st century literacy (information, digital and visual) among students and faculty.
- Reaching and engaging today's learner.
- Encouraging faculty adoption and innovation in teaching and learning with IT.
- Advancing innovation in teaching and learning with technology in an era of budget cuts.
- Behaviour management is a constant challenge and the intricacies of the learner should be known and worked upon to bring out the best.
- Effective teaming leads to better results for both students and the teachers. Establishing a team and working towards its continued success through regular productive interaction is another sensitive challenge.
- The challenge of meeting students with different interests, abilities, skills and knowledge and catering to the variety of needs that are confronted with is the need of the hour.

INDIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM: An birds eye view:- India has been on a strong growth path and the country's GDP has grown at around 8.5% over FY2003-08. In spite of this tremendous growth, India still lies at an abysmal 132nd position among 179 countries on human development index published by United Nations Development Programme. This illustrates that the gains of growth have not translated into a rise in living standard for the masses. Nowhere is this apparent more than in education, India is 97th among 135 developing countries in the Human Education Index. Education has so far played a crucial role in the economic and social progress of independent India, but still a lot is needed. Emphasis on expansion is necessary to ensure that every child has an equal opportunity to study. The quality in most of our educational institutions is below par and expansion must be done without diluting standards. Excellence needs to be supported by inclusion for all segments of the society to ensure uniform development. Thus, the objectives of reform in education should be expansion, excellence and inclusion. Some of the reasons behind this dichotomy in growth and development are described below:

- **Lack of balanced Expenditure**
- **Inadequate Public Infrastructure**
 - Lower access to Upper-Primary education
 - Lack of basic facilities & number of teachers
 - Inadequate Higher Education facilities
 - Ineffective Vocational Training
 - Regulatory & Legal hurdles
 - Lack of agricultural focus

ACHIEVEMENTS OF GOOD EDUCATION SYSTEM

Apart from solving the problems mentioned above, economy and society can be transformed in a significant way if we improve the spread and the quality of education. Some of the ways are-

Realization of demographic dividend- India is a young country in an ageing world economy. In 2020 India is projected to have an additional 47 million workers, almost equal to the total world shortfall. The average Indian will be only 29 years old, compared to 37 in USA, 45 in Western Europe and 48 in Japan.

Workforce crunch in Indian Labour Markets- Some 81% of Indian companies believe that lack of human resources will be the single largest deterrent to speedy development. Only a quarter of all graduates are employed and ~80% of the job seekers in employment exchange are without any professional skills. Companies are able to select only eight/nine people out of 100 applicants which is a pretty low selection ratio. This has created huge requirements for talent in the sectors like hospitality, retail, aviation & like.

Contribution to Human Development- Education can facilitate human development by opening up avenues of employment and raising incomes. A rise in education acts as an endowment which allows people to become aware of their rights and take advantage of government floated schemes. Development indicators related to fertility and health can be improved by educating women. Also when you educate a woman, you typically educate a family. In India, around 4.5 crore children officially and around 7-8 crore unofficially, are out of schools and end up as laborers.

According to International Labour Organization, abolition of child labour will increase the India's GDP by \$1,000 billion as children move from labour markets to schools. Indian and international experience shows a clear link between the growth of education and fall in child labour.

INDIA EDUCATION SECTORS & CHALLENGES AHEAD: *The National Knowledge Commission has come out with a list of recommendations to ensure expansion, excellence and inclusion in the Indian education sector. The main recommendations are:-*

Expansion of the industry:

a) Create more universities- Open 1500 universities nationwide to help India attain a gross enrolment ratio of 15 per cent by 2015. Both public and private sector have a role to play in this expansion.

b) Simplify regulatory system- Establish an Independent Regulatory Authority for Higher Education (IRAHE) to replace bodies such as AICTE and monitor standards.

2. Maintain Excellence

a) Reform existing universities- Curricula should be revised once in three years and evaluation should include continuous internal assessment. Universities must become the hub of research once again to capture synergies between teaching and research. Infrastructure that supports teaching-learning process, such as libraries and laboratories needs to be monitored and upgraded on a regular basis.

b) Promote enhanced quality- There should be stringent information disclosure norms for all educational institutions on their financials, assets, admissions criteria, faculty positions, curricula and accreditation. Evaluation of courses and teachers by students as well as peers should be encouraged.

3. Ensure Inclusion

a) Access for all deserving students- A 'needs blind admissions' policy should be adopted to ensure no student is forced to leave studies because of financial constraints. Extensive National Scholarship Scheme should target economically underprivileged students and students from historically socially disadvantaged groups.

b) Affirmative action- The access to education of students from socially disadvantaged groups should be facilitated by incorporating flexible, sensitive schooling strategies and learning aids. Study material should be developed in local languages as high demand exists for it.

STEPS SHOULD BE TAKEN TO :-

- Attract students to basic sciences to build a strong foundation in mathematics and science. This will create the next generation of competent scientific talent and teachers.
- More agricultural universities should be opened to develop talent to increase research and development in agriculture for achieving higher productivity.
- Accountability can be improved by including both process and outcome indicators for institutions.
- The science curricula and content should be revamped to increase research components and hands-on work.
- Memory, comprehension and creativity should all be tested to increase engagement in studies.
- Vocational training institutes should be revamped and tie up with industry to allow the deployment of talent from day one.

Challenges faced by Indian education sector:

"The higher education sector in India faces numerous challenges today. On the one hand, there is need for increasing access and making education affordable. On the other, there is need to ensure quality and pursue excellence," "Not many international students come to India for higher studies either," he said. "it is a worrying sign that the number of students from seven out of the top eight countries in this respect - US, Germany, France, South Korea, Australia, China and Singapore - have dipped 73 per cent in 2014".

"The developmental challenges faced by our country call for an inspired response from the higher education system. Quality and relevant research can help tide over our socio-economic problems,"

Research in higher education institutions is at its lowest ebb. There is an inadequate and diminishing financial support for higher education from the government and from society. Many colleges established in rural areas are non-viable, are under-enrolled and have extremely poor infrastructure and facilities with just a few teachers. A series of judicial interventions over the last two decades and knee-jerk reaction of the government – both at the centre and state level and the regulatory bodies without proper understanding of the emerging market structure of higher education in India has further added confusion to the higher education landscape in the country. There is an absence of a well-informed reform agenda for higher education in the country. A few efforts made now and then are not rooted in the new global realities based on competition and increased mobility of students and workforce.

THE SOLUTION IDENTIFIED FOR COMMON CONCERNS:

- A lack of understanding of science and engineering and associated careers
- A need to encourage creativity in science and engineering, teacher training, secondary and primary science education
- A need for information, learning and teaching material on the history of science, engineering and technology and society issues at all levels
- Increasing problems regarding number and quality of students going into science at secondary level, and into science and engineering education at universities
- Various problems of science and engineering education at university, secondary and primary school level were recognized, and the need for new models of education and training curricula and pedagogy based on active, inquiry-based learning
- A need to share information on and promote active, practice- and inquiry-based learning in science and engineering Needs for greater linkage and cooperation between university educators, schools and industry, secondary and primary science educators
- A need for better networking between formal and informal science and engineering educators
- A need to encourage participation of women and underrepresented groups in science and engineering education.

OPPORTUNITIES IN EDUCATION SECTOR:

Education industry has several exciting and high-income options that entrepreneurs can adopt. The options primarily divide into four sections namely : **Producer, Service Provider, Facilitator, Trader** .

Producer :- As producer, the entrepreneur will create learning objects in digital format that are sold out rightly or on royalty basis to various elearning companies, alternatively the producer can enter the market as service provider and sell the material themselves. Typical digital learning objects include e-books, lessons, lesson plans, presentations, notes, question data banks, audio, videos etc.

Service Provider :- As service provider, the entrepreneur will undertake online teaching or online training himself or herself. Depending on the nature of the education i.e. academic, skill training or vocational, the entrepreneur can create business model on sale or subscription basis. This segment of education industry has an extreme high earning potential and has the extreme advantage of high customer loyalty. Once again, the entrepreneur can choose between active teaching or/and passive mentoring, possibilities are numerous and all of them are highly rewarding.

Facilitator :- Business for medium to large enterprise where the entrepreneur creates the virtual infrastructure that can be utilized by the home based and small-scale enterprises to carry out their business. The Role of the entrepreneur is of an application service provider who creates the infrastructure and software that are further purchased or subscribed to by individuals and SME. The segment has high cost factor compared to other segments but once established it is virtual goldmine.

Trader :- The best example to quote here would be site like amazon.com that helps the publishers across the globe sell their books and digital products. Entrepreneur in this segment acts like a medium between buyer and seller and helps both sides achieve their objectives. The name amazon.com is purely for reference and it is not for scaring the readers that the business is possible only at extremely large scale. The segment suits all level of entrepreneurs who can act as mediums and connect the buyer seller. The segment is not confined to books alone in fact it is not confined to digital mediums either there are several components in education that can be adopted by the entrepreneur. Industry is paying, opportunities are numerous and last but not the least it is not necessary to be an educator to enter the education industry.

CONCLUSION

It is believed that based on the current and future manpower requirements of the various sectors, there is a huge demand-supply gap in the education space. This has attracted many players to invest in education and training institutions with the aim of building valuable franchises that can be rapidly scaled up and has necessitated the restructuring of educational systems to suit the changing circumstances. These challenges can be addressed by the education system by tying up with corporate sector and by using modern technologies as well as by going in for innovative programs. Active learning is emphasized in contemporary learning theory, which finds that interactions leads to greater student engagement, retention leads to greater student engagement, retention and competence. An innovative combination of technology and pedagogy should be developed to make learning more interactive. The learning space whether a classroom, a laboratory, a library or an informal space can enhance learning. It can go beyond the physical to virtual. Teaching does not necessarily result in learning. Students differ in learning styles and characteristics.

Flexible and blended learning, online access to programmes and resources and self assessment tools can be alternatives to enhance successful learning. Inventions of Internet technologies have enriched education. They provide easy, fast and cost effective ways creating, sharing and distribution of education material as digital lessons at a mass scale. They also allow the learners to self-access and improve their performance without public embarrassment. Internet has created online learning or E-learning as it is popularly called which has made education truly Whenever, Wherever, Whatever. It has changed the way the education is conceived, distributed and delivered and significantly reduced the costs attached to it.

Good teachers are a depleting resource but thanks to internet technologies this problem now is countered as thoughts and teachings of these great teachers can be preserved in form of digital lessons e.g. digital notes, e-Book, presentations, Audio lessons, Video lessons etc. Digital lessons and online teaching and training have removed the logistics and commuting problems faced by many organizations. Today by using e-learning, Organizations teach and train masses at fraction of the cost earlier incurred in much lesser period.

The benefits of e-learning leave little to wonder as to why the teachers and learners are not only accepting online methods of educating across the globe but also the demands for online teaching and training are growing at phenomenal pace. One major advantage internet technologies offer education industry is the cost inputs that are required which stand at fraction of costs incurred earlier in brick and mortar system of education. Establishing a virtual infrastructure for educating is faster, cheaper and much more effective in several ways.

Entrepreneurs can enter the education industry at any level i.e. self employed, work from home enterprise, small and medium enterprise or a large-scale enterprise. This industry has many opportunities at every level and has relative faster growth and high scalability compared to many other industries.

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